

**O'ZGARUVCHAN KO'RSATKICHLI KUCHLI NOLINEAR
 DIFFUZIYA-REAKTSIYA TENGLAMALARINING AVTOMODEL VA
 SONLI YECHIMLARI**

J. M. Toshtemirov¹, S. Toxirov²

Qarshi state university, Qarshi, Uzbekistan¹

University of science and technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan^{1,2}

jaloliddintoshtemirov0@gmail.com¹

Annotatsiya: Maqolada kuchli nolinear diffuziya va reaksiya jarayonlarini ifodalovchi quyidagi tenglama:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \left(u^{m-1} |\nabla u^k|^{p-2} \nabla u \right) + u^a - u^b$$

uchun nazariy tahlil, avtomodel (o'z-o'ziga o'xshash) yechimlar va sonli hisoblash algoritmlari ishlab chiqiladi. Sonli yechimlar grafiklar orqali tasdiqlanadi. Olingan natijalar ushbu turdagi tenglamalarning fizik, biologik va kimyoviy modellashtirishdagi qo'llanilishi uchun asos yaratadi.

Nolinear parabolik tenglamalar ko'plab fizik, biologik va kimyoviy jarayonlarning matematik modelini ifodalaydi. Masalan, kimyoviy moddaning tarqalishi va reaksiyasi, biologik populyatsiyalar evolyutsiyasi, issiqlik tarqalishi kabi. Ushbu maqolada o'rganilayotgan tenglama quyidagicha:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \left(u^{m-1} |\nabla u^k|^{p-2} \nabla u \right) + u^a - u^b$$

Tenglama kuchli nolinear diffuziya va nolinear reaksiya komponentlarini o'z ichiga oladi, bu esa analitik yechim topishni murakkablashtiradi. Shu sababdan avtomodel yondashuvi va sonli metodlar qo'llaniladi.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \left(u^{m-1} |\nabla u^k|^{p-2} \nabla u \right) + u^a - u^b, \quad x \in \Omega, \quad t > 0, \quad (1)$$

$$u(t, x) = 0, \quad x \in \partial\Omega, \quad t > 0, \quad (2)$$

$$u(0, x) = u_0(x), \quad x \in \Omega, \quad (3)$$

bu yerda $n, m, k > 1, p > 2, a > 1, b \geq 1, a \neq b$ va $\Omega \subset R^N$ esa silliq chegara $\partial\Omega$ bilan chegaralangan sohadir.

Mazkur tezisda nochizikli manba va yutilishga ega nochizikli diffuziya jarayonlarini matematik modellashtirish, tahlil qilish va sonli yechish bilan bog'liq

asosiy vazifalar ko'rib chiqilgan. Ushbu vazifalar, nazariy tahlil, sonli usullar va dasturiy ta'minotni ishlab chiqish orqali hal qilingan:

Taqqoslash printsipli, noxiziqli ajratish usuli va avtomodel tahlil kabi metodlar yordamida tenglama va tenglamalar sistemasi uchun yechimning global mavjudlik va chegaralanmaganlik shartlari olingan. Ushbu natijalardan o'zgarmas va o'zgaruvchan zichlikli diffuziya modellari sifat xossalarini aniqlashda foydalanilgan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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